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Project Newsletter

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Key Research Findings: Retail MSMEs and AI Adoption

Over the past months, our team has been working to **uncover the AI skills gaps and needs** of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) in the retail sector.

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Looking Ahead: the AI Core Curriculum

One of INAIR's most significant outcomes is the development of an AI Core Curriculum designed specifically for retail MSMEs. It will provide companies with the tools and knowledge they need to **upskill their workforce and integrate AI into their business models**.

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Spreading the Word: INAIR's Dissemination Efforts

Our project team has been actively engaged in various dissemination efforts to promote the findings and insights from the project to a wider audience.

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KEY RESEARCH FINDINGS: RETAIL MSMEs AND AI ADOPTION

UNCOVERING CHALLENGES AND OPPORTUNITIES IN AI INTEGRATION FOR EUROPEAN RETAIL

Over the past seven months, our consortium has been working to identify the AI skills gaps and needs of micro, small, and medium-sized enterprises (MSMEs) in the retail sector across five European countries: Cyprus, Germany, Italy, Poland, and Romania.

The research work - conducted by sociologists, economists and data scientists from the **Digital Economy Lab of the University of Warsaw** and supported by the other consortium members, included **desk research** and **co-creation workshops** with relevant industry experts, complemented by a comprehensive **literature review**, the **analysis of nearly 45,000 job advertisements** relevant to AI in retail and **statistical analysis** on AI implementation within MSMEs in the countries studied.

Our research has revealed several critical insights into the current state of AI adoption and the challenges faced by MSMEs in the retail sector across Europe:

- 💡 **AI adoption is still limited:** Despite the increasing role of digital technologies, AI use in the retail sector remains in its early stages, with barriers such as fragmented sectors, insufficient digital skills, and low levels of digitalisation in certain regions, particularly in Poland and Romania.
- 💡 **Low demand for AI-skilled workers:** Employers in the retail sector have yet to fully recognise AI's transformative potential, as reflected in the limited demand for AI-skilled workers.
- 💡 **Diverse applications of AI:** For companies already adopting AI, applications vary widely, including optimising customer service, automating recruitment, and managing inventory. See Chapter 3 of our report for detailed use cases.
- 💡 **The digital mindset:** The shift towards AI requires not only technical skills but also a "digital mindset" - openness to innovation, collaboration with technology, and the ability to learn continuously.

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external link to the research report on Zenodo

CO-CREATION WORKSHOPS: COLLABORATIVE SOLUTIONS FOR AI SKILLS

One of the most exciting and innovative aspects of the research work was the co-creation workshops held with the retail sector stakeholders, including business owners, managers, and employees. Through these online interactive sessions, we were able to identify the critical AI skills that MSMEs need to thrive in an increasingly digital economy.

A glimpse into the workshop process and outcomes:

A Collaborative Approach

The co-creation workshops were a platform for real dialogue between MSME stakeholders and AI experts. Participants shared their experiences, challenges, and visions for the future of AI in their businesses. These sessions were not just about knowledge transfer; they were about creating a shared understanding of AI's role in retail.

Identifying Critical AI Skills

Workshop participants highlighted several key skills that are essential for leveraging AI technologies effectively. These included data analysis, customer relationship management, and digital marketing skills, among others. Managers, in particular, need strategic planning capabilities to integrate AI within their companies, while workers require basic computer literacy and openness to ongoing learning.

Practical Solutions

The workshops didn't just identify challenges—they also offered solutions. Participants proposed tailored educational programs and resources to bridge the current skills gap. Their input was crucial in shaping the AI Core Curriculum, which we are developing to help MSMEs navigate their digital transformation journey.

LOOKING AHEAD: THE AI CORE CURRICULUM FOR RETAILERS

PREPARING RETAIL MSMEs FOR AI INTEGRATION WITH TAILORED EDUCATIONAL RESOURCES

One of the most significant outcomes of the INAIR project is the development of a dedicated AI Core Curriculum tailored specifically for MSMEs in the retail sector. This curriculum is designed to equip businesses with the essential tools and knowledge to upskill their workforce and seamlessly integrate AI into their business models. By focusing on both technical and transversal skills, the curriculum ensures that companies are well-prepared to adopt AI technologies in alignment with their operational goals and customer needs.

The INAIR project has identified several key skills critical for the successful adoption of AI in retail MSMEs. These include technical skills such as data analysis, customer relationship management (CRM), and digital marketing, alongside transversal skills like strategic planning and change management. Central to these findings is the concept of a "digital mindset"—an attitude that embraces innovation, adapts to technological changes, and fosters continuous learning. Retail employees must build a solid foundation in basic digital literacy, while managers need the ability to strategically integrate AI into their business operations.

The research also underscores the importance of fostering a culture of collaboration with new technologies and encouraging a willingness to acquire new competencies. These skills are essential for successfully navigating the ongoing digital transformation within the retail sector. Currently, these insights are being incorporated into the AI Core Curriculum, which is **scheduled for release in January 2025.**

SPREADING THE WORD: INAIR'S DISSEMINATION EFFORTS

RAISING AWARENESS AND SHARING THE POTENTIAL OF AI IN RETAIL

Our project team has been actively engaged in various dissemination efforts to promote the findings and insights from the INAIR project to a wider audience. Below are some of the key dissemination activities that highlight our ongoing commitment to spreading awareness about AI in the retail sector:

- **Presentations at European Events:** The INAIR project was presented during the "Present Your Business" event organised by the European Digital SME Alliance, providing an excellent platform to engage with businesses and discuss the transformative power of AI in the retail sector. Another major event was the "Young Citizens Conference" held at Ovidius Highschool in Constanta, which was part of the *MILSET Young Citizens Conferences* series, focusing on how AI can elevate shopping experiences.
- **Collaborations:** We have established partnerships with academic institutions such as Universitatea Maritimă din Constanța, where AI applications and educational programs were showcased. Furthermore, interactive sessions during events like [AI4YouthWork](#) Erasmus+ initiatives and Art for Action competitions have sparked conversations about how AI can revolutionise sectors like retail and youth employment. The project was also presented during the opening lecture by prof. Renata Włoch for 300 representatives of the 4U+ Alliance of European Universities.
- **Industry Webinars:** The INAIR team was part of a webinar titled "*Intelligenza Artificiale nel Retail: Rivoluzionare l'Esperienza del Cliente e Ottimizzare le Operazioni*" organised by Eurosportello Confesercenti and CenTraTech in partnership with major retail players like CONAD DAO Soc. Coop. and Custom Group. This webinar discussed how AI-driven personalization and advanced tools like predictive analytics and heat mapping can improve retail performance. Prof. Katarzyna Śledziwska from DELab UW also presented INAIR at the "Artificial Intelligence in Business and Everyday Life" conference, discussing the potential use of generative AI in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs), revealing research outcomes from the INAIR project.
- **Strategic Discussions with Policymakers:** The project was also presented to key representatives from the European Commission's DG GROW, UNIEuropa, EuroCommerce, and JA Europe during meetings focused on the Pact 4 Skills' Large-Scale Partnership for the Retail Ecosystem. Researchers from DELab shared insights from their comprehensive study on AI skills gaps in retail, sparking interest among EU policymakers.

- **Workshops on AI in Retail:** At the invitation of the Chamber of the Digital Economy, Prof. Katarzyna Śledziwska and Prof. Renata Włoch led a workshop titled "How is AI Revolutionising the Retail Sector in Poland?" This workshop provided an opportunity to share early findings from the INAIR study and discuss both the benefits and challenges of AI adoption in retail, with a focus on the diverse skill sets required for future AI adopters.
- **Presentations for the wide public:** during Warsaw Science Festival, the largest science popularisation event in Poland Dr. Agata Komendant-Brodowska from the INAIR project team presented "AI behind the counter and in the warehouse," on AI's transformative role in retail. The session attracted curious participants eager to learn about AI's impact on modern business practices.
- **Social Media Promotion:** We have leveraged multiple social media platforms to promote the INAIR project and its co-creation workshops, reaching audiences through [Instagram](#), [Facebook](#) and [LinkedIn](#). These campaigns highlighted our workshops in Germany and the release of key reports by DELab UW, ensuring that a wide audience stays informed about our progress and findings.

Through these activities, we aim to ensure that the research findings of the INAIR project reach a broad spectrum of stakeholders, from SMEs and policy makers to academia and the general public. **We will continue our efforts to spread knowledge about the essential AI skills that can transform the retail sector and empower MSMEs to adopt AI technologies.**

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Join the AI Revolution

The AI revolution is here, and MSMEs have a unique opportunity to be at the forefront of this transformation. While challenges remain, the potential benefits of AI adoption in the retail sector are immense. With the right skills and strategies in place, MSMEs can unlock new levels of efficiency, customer satisfaction, and competitiveness. **We encourage all stakeholders to get involved**, whether by participating in future co-creation workshops, sharing your AI success stories, or joining us in developing the AI Core Curriculum.

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